

1 **Glacial Isostatic Adjustment reduces past and future**
2 **Arctic subsea permafrost**

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9 Abstract

10 Sea-level rise submerges terrestrial permafrost in the Arctic, turning it into sub-
11 sea permafrost. Subsea permafrost underlies ~ 1.8 million km² of Arctic continental shelf,
12 with thicknesses in places exceeding 700 m. Sea-level variations over glacial-interglacial
13 cycles control subsea permafrost distribution and thickness, yet no permafrost model has
14 accounted for glacial isostatic adjustment (GIA), which deviates local sea level from the
15 global mean due to changes in ice and ocean loading. We incorporate GIA into a pan-
16 Arctic model of subsea permafrost over the last 400,000 years. Including GIA significantly
17 reduces present-day subsea permafrost thickness, chiefly because of hydro-isostatic ef-
18 fects as well as deformation related to Northern Hemisphere ice sheets. Additionally, we
19 extend the simulation 1000 years into the future for emissions scenarios outlined in the
20 International Panel on Climate Change’s sixth assessment report. We find that subsea
21 permafrost is preserved under a low emissions scenario but mostly disappears under a
22 high emissions scenario.

23 1 Introduction

24 Sea-level lowstands during past glacial periods exposed the Arctic continental shelf
25 to cold air temperatures that froze the ground, forming up to a kilometer of new per-
26 mafrost (Schirrmeister et al., 2011). Postglacial sea-level rise inundated much of this cry-
27 otic sediment, producing subsea permafrost, which began to thaw as oceanic heat and
28 salt propagated downwards from the seafloor (Romanovskii et al., 2004). Permafrost is
29 defined here as sediment above or below sea level that has temperature at or below 0 °C
30 for at least two years and may or may not contain ice. While present-day subsea per-
31 mafrost thaws due to geothermal heat from below and ocean warming from above, more
32 is created at an accelerating rate as terrestrial permafrost turns into subsea permafrost
33 through coastal erosion (Jones et al., 2009) and sea-level rise (Proshutinsky et al., 2001,
34 2004).

35 The need to track human carbon dioxide emissions (CO_2) has driven assessments
36 of the global carbon budget, including the amount and stability of the carbon reservoir
37 below the ocean floor (Friedlingstein et al., 2020, 2022). Ongoing debate surrounding how
38 much carbon from thawing subsea permafrost will reach the atmosphere (Ruppel & Kessler,
39 2017; Shakhova et al., 2014; P. Overduin et al., 2016) has precluded subsea permafrost’s
40 inclusion in global carbon budgets. Recent work and structured expert assessment, how-
41 ever, suggest that the submarine permafrost domain holds an amount of carbon in or-
42 ganic matter and methane hydrates of similar magnitude to the Earth’s total gas reserves
43 (Sayedi et al., 2020; Ruppel & Kessler, 2017; Gilfillan et al., 2019). Rising Arctic water
44 temperatures in the coming century, projected under all emissions scenarios, will has-
45 ten subsea permafrost thaw (Wilkenskjeld et al., 2021). Accelerated permafrost thaw rates
46 will increase carbon mobilization rates beneath the seabed. Since this carbon may reach
47 the atmosphere as greenhouse gas, it is important to have an estimate for the amount
48 of carbon currently trapped in and by permafrost, its stability, and the timing of its re-
49 lease.

50 Such an estimate requires accurate quantification of how much subsea permafrost
51 exists today. Regional maps of present subsea permafrost extent typically rely on a com-
52 bination of observations and physics-based modeling (D. J. Nicolsky et al., 2012; Broth-
53 ers et al., 2016). The International Permafrost Association (IPA) permafrost map, an
54 early pan-Arctic effort, applied the heuristic that permafrost would exist anywhere where
55 the shelf was exposed for long enough during sea-level lowstands to establish permafrost,
56 implying unglaciated regions shallower than around 100 m (Brown et al., 1997). More
57 recently, subsea permafrost was mapped in a consistent manner at circum-Arctic spa-
58 tial scale over the last 450 thousand years (P. P. Overduin et al., 2019) by forcing a heat
59 transfer model with spatially-varying geothermal heat flux, depth-varying ocean bottom

60 water temperature, sediment porosity, global mean sea level (GMSL) from a Red Sea oxy-
61 gen isotope record (Grant et al., 2014), and ice sheet thicknesses and air temperature
62 from the CLIMBER2 Earth System Model (Ganopolski et al., 2010).

63 Sea level and ice history are the most important controls on subsea permafrost for-
64 mation. Together, they determine the fraction of time Arctic sediments are exposed to
65 (relatively) warm temperatures beneath ice sheets or oceans rather than to cold air tem-
66 perature. In Arctic shelf regions beyond the maximal extents of the Northern Hemispheric
67 ice sheets, inundation time controls the distribution, depth, and density of subsea per-
68 mafrost (Angelopoulos et al., 2020). Extant subsea permafrost calculations have included
69 GMSL as a forcing term (Romanovskii et al., 2004; P. P. Overduin et al., 2019; D. Nicol-
70 sky & Shakhova, 2010). However, local sea level at locations on the Arctic shelf devi-
71 ates from GMSL (Klemann et al., 2015) due to glacial isostatic adjustment (GIA), which
72 is the gravitational, deformational, and rotational response of the solid Earth to ice and
73 liquid water loading (Farrell & Clark, 1976). In the GIA literature, local sea level is also
74 often referred to as relative sea level (RSL), which is defined as sea level at a given lo-
75 cation and time relative to present-day sea level at the same location.

76 The deviation between local and global mean sea level is particularly pronounced
77 near Banks Island and in the Barents and Kara Seas—where ice sheet loading deformed
78 the solid earth by hundreds of meters over glacial cycles—and along the western Laptev
79 Sea and North Slope, which underwent peripheral bulge uplift and subsidence (Lambeck,
80 1995; Lakeman & England, 2014). Even in places far from the Northern Hemisphere ice
81 sheets at Last Glacial Maximum (LGM, ~ 26.5 to 19 thousand years before present (kyr
82 BP)), such as the East Siberian Sea, changing water loading over glacial cycles can cause
83 RSL to deviate from GMSL by 10+ meters (Klemann et al., 2015). Since these changes
84 in local sea-level history can lengthen or shorten the duration of land inundation or seabed
85 exposure for large portions of the Arctic shelf, we hypothesize that their omission leads
86 to nonuniform biases in estimates of subsea permafrost distribution, thickness, and thaw
87 rate.

88 Here we test this hypothesis by extending the subsea permafrost model of P. P. Over-
89 duin et al. (2019) to include RSL produced by GIA modeling. We isolate the effects of
90 GIA by comparing permafrost extents from a simulation that includes spatially vary-
91 ing RSL to two that do not. We explore whether the inclusion of GIA in numerically mod-
92 eled subsea permafrost improves correspondence between modeled and measured sub-
93 sea permafrost extent. We further explore the effect of future warming scenarios on sub-
94 sea permafrost distribution by extending models that do and do not include GIA to year
95 3000 under a range of ice melt scenarios related to shared socioeconomic pathways (SSPs,
96 hereafter 'emissions pathways') from the International Panel on Climate Change's 6th
97 Assessment report (IPCC, Fox-Kemper, B. et al., 2021).

98 2 Results

99 Subsea permafrost distribution and state on the Arctic continental shelf was sim-
100 ulated from 400 kyr BP to the pre-industrial (1850 CE) using three model configurations:
101 (1) the CLIMBER2 ice history (Ganopolski et al., 2010) and GMSL from Grant et al.
102 (2014) without GIA (hereafter *legacy* run); (2) the ICE6G ice history (Peltier et al., 2015)
103 and GMSL curve prior to the LGM from (Waelbroeck et al., 2002) without GIA (here-
104 after *base* run); and (3) the ICE6G ice history and GMSL curve prior to LGM from Waelbroeck
105 et al. (2002) with GIA (hereafter *GIA* run, see Methods). The subsea permafrost cal-
106 culation was extended from 1850 CE to 3000 CE for the *GIA* and *base* runs using 17 dif-
107 ferent future ice sheet configurations based on the ISMIP6 ensemble (Chambers et al.,
108 2021; Greve & Chambers, 2021) and climate forcing scenarios from the IPCC-AR6 (see
109 Methods). The *GIA* run is presented hereafter, and we demonstrate and explain how changes
110 in model setup between the *legacy* run, which resembles P. P. Overduin et al. (2019) (see

111 Methods), the *base* run, and the *GIA* run affect our modeling results. Permafrost was
 112 modeled between 187 m below and 18 m above present-day sea level at every location on
 113 the Arctic continental shelf and nearshore. The total modeled permafrost area is defined
 114 as the sum of modeled regions whose depth profiles included terrestrial or subsea per-
 115 mafrost. Sedimentation rates, mineral conductivity, geothermal heat flux, and vertical
 116 conductive heat flux were parameterized following P. P. Overduin et al. (2019). At ev-
 117 ery time step in the resulting permafrost distribution, we removed permafrost from lo-
 118 cations where warm bottom water from present-day rivers, deltas, and estuaries likely
 119 precludes permafrost formation (P. P. Overduin et al., 2019).

120 2.1 Past evolution and present-day extent

121 The temporal evolution of subsea permafrost, as measured by mean thickness, re-
 122 sponds to Earth’s sawtooth history of ice volume change (Fig. 1). The mean thickness
 123 of permafrost in the total model area increases during glaciations as sea level falls and
 124 exposes the shelf to cold air temperatures. Subsea permafrost is generally absent dur-
 125 ing these times since the continental shelves are exposed. Deglaciation inundates con-
 126 tinental shelves and turns terrestrial permafrost into subsea permafrost, which quickly
 127 thaws as warm ocean waters increase temperatures on the shelf. After interglacials, sub-
 128 sea permafrost continues to thaw until it disappears or is converted to terrestrial per-
 129 mafrost by falling sea level. In the *GIA* run, the mean thickness of permafrost in our to-
 130 tal modeled area peaks at 500-550 m during glacial maxima and thins to 125-150 m by
 131 the end of interglacials (Fig. 1B).

Figure 1. Timeseries of subsea permafrost thickness and global mean sea level (GMSL). (A) GMSL from Waelbroeck et al. (2002) and Peltier et al. (2015) (past); Chambers et al. (2021) and Greve, Calov, et al. (2020) (future, see Methods). Marine isotope stages (MIS) are indicated following Railsback et al. (2015). (B) Mean subsea permafrost thickness (dark teal) between 400 kyr BP and 1850 CE for the *GIA* run. Mean permafrost thickness in the total modeled area (light teal). Subsea permafrost thickness for low (SSP1-2.6, blue) and high (SSP5-8.5, purple) emissions scenarios.

132 Based on the *GIA* run, subsea permafrost presently underlies 1.8×10^6 km² of the
 133 Arctic continental shelf and has a mean thickness of 253 m. Subsea permafrost reaches
 134 a maximum thickness of 708 m in shallow sediments offshore of Yukagir in the central
 135 Laptev Sea. Permafrost that exceeds a thickness of 500 m also underlies the shallow cen-
 136 tral Kara Sea and the westernmost coastline of the Alaskan North Slope, while much of
 137 the deeper Chukchi and East Siberian Seas cover subsea permafrost that is less than 200 m
 138 thick (Fig. 2A, see Fig. 5A for locations).

Figure 2. (A) Subsea permafrost thickness at 1850 for the *GIA* model run. (B) Same as (A), but for the *legacy* model run. (C) Same as (A) but with the *base* run. (D) The difference in permafrost thickness between the *base* and *legacy* model runs (i.e. C-B). (E) The difference in permafrost thickness between the *GIA* and *base* model runs (i.e. A-C). Areas in (D) and (E) with >200 m difference in permafrost thickness are locations where additional permafrost is introduced in the *base* and *GIA* cases, respectively.

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2.1.1 Ice history & Global mean sea-level curve

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The choice of ice history affects present-day subsea permafrost. When compared to subsea permafrost estimates from the *legacy* run, adopting the *base* run results in thicker present-day cryotic sediment on the deep Russian continental shelf and nearly all the Canadian arctic by >50 m, but yields thinner cryotic sediment on much of the shallow Russian continental shelf by 200–250 m and in the eastern Kara Sea by >500 m (fig. 2B).

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These patterns are explained by the differing GMSL and ice distributions in the *base* and *legacy* runs. GMSL in the *base* run is generally higher early in glacial intervals (MIS 11b–10b, 9d–8b, 7b–6b, 5d–3a) than GMSL in the *legacy* run, but lower during peak glacials (MIS 10a, 7d, 6a, 2, Fig. 3). Higher early-glacial GMSL inhibits the formation of shallow subsea permafrost by decreasing subaerial exposure time; lower peak-glacial GMSL enhances subsea permafrost formation on the deep shelf (Fig. 3). The >500 m thickness difference in the eastern Kara Sea is caused by differences in ice distribution. CLIMBER2, which drives the *legacy* run and employs the SICOPOLIS polythermal ice model, simulates a small Eurasian Ice Sheet (EIS) with little ice east of the western Kara Sea at glacial maxima, while in the *base* run maximal ice extent crosses the Kara Sea to the Severnaya Zemlya archipelago, inhibiting permafrost formation in that region. While the GMSL and ice history of the last glacial cycle have the largest impact on present-day subsea permafrost distribution, conditions during the earlier glacial cycles, particularly the penultimate cycle, also affect present-day permafrost thickness and ice content. Overall, using the *base* ice history decreases the area of seafloor presently underlain by permafrost by 4×10^5 km² and the mean thickness of that permafrost by 44 m compared to the *legacy* run.

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Though sea level modulates the fraction of time that Arctic sediments spend exposed to air, water, and ice, the variable that drives permafrost formation directly is surface forcing temperature. Mean surface forcing temperature was calculated at each location from the local history of sea-level, glacial load, and air temperature (Fig. 4, see Methods). Since air temperatures are chosen to be the same in the *legacy*, *base*, and *GIA* runs, changes in surface forcing temperature are driven by varying sea-level curves and ice sheet histories, and therefore resemble permafrost thickness changes in Fig. 2B & C. The change from *legacy* to *base* run diminishes temperature forcing—i.e. the mean surface temperatures of the *base* run are cooler than those relative to the *legacy* run—in much of the Canadian arctic, the deepest areas of the Laptev and East Siberian Seas, around the New Siberian Islands, and near the White Sea (Fig. 4A). In these regions, subsea permafrost in the *base* run is thicker than in the *legacy* run (2B). Areas where *base* run mean temperature forcing is warmer than the *legacy* run, and subsea permafrost consequently thinner, include the Laptev Sea and the shallower parts of the East Siberian and Chukchi Seas.

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2.1.2 GIA effects on present-day subsea permafrost distribution

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Present-day subsea permafrost distribution and state is significantly influenced by GIA. The inclusion of GIA in the model reduces the area of Arctic shelf that is underlain by cryotic sediments at 1850 CE from 2.1×10^6 to 1.8×10^6 km², i.e. by 14%.

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GIA causes systematic deviations in RSL on the Arctic continental shelf. These deviations are chiefly due to glacial loading, peripheral bulge dynamics, and hydro-isostasy. Gravitational effects tend to be smaller since the rebounding Earth in part counteracts the gravitational effects from melting ice sheets (Supplemental Fig. S1). The EIS inhibits permafrost formation in all but the shallowest areas of the Barents and Kara Seas. In those shallow regions where permafrost is present, direct isostatic loading increases sea level when covered by the EIS, as seen in the >80 m rise in GIA in the Kara Sea during glacial maxima (Fig. 5C, D). Peripheral bulges around the EIS and Laurentide ice

Figure 3. Global mean sea-level curves between 400 ka and present. Blue filled envelope represents times when the GMSL curve of Waelbroeck et al. (2002), used in the *GIA* and *base* runs, is deeper than the GMSL curve of Grant et al. (2014), used in the *legacy* run; brown envelope represents times when the Waelbroeck et al. (2002) curve is shallower. Numbers and letters along top edge represent Marine Isotope Stages (MIS) as defined in Railsback et al. (2015). Darker grey bars indicate MIS sub-stages during which substantial subsea permafrost is formed.

Figure 4. Mean temperature forcing change between subsea permafrost experiments. (A) Difference in mean forcing temperature between *legacy* and *base* runs. (B) Difference in mean forcing temperature between *base* and *GIA* runs.

189 lead to negative GIA (RSL is lower than GMSL) (Fig. 5B) and the shape and location
 190 of this feature evolves through time.

191 Outboard of the peripheral bulge, hydro-isostasy exerts a dominant influence on
 192 RSL (Fig. 5B). Hydro-isostasy is the GIA response to changing water load: ice melt dur-

Figure 5. (A) Topography of the Arctic continental shelf at Last Glacial Maximum (26 ka) in meters above sea level. Colored dots indicate exemplary locations in the East Siberian (red), Laptev (blue), and Kara (purple) seas. Other labeled sites include Banks Island, the Alaskan North Slope, the Chukchi Sea, the Severnaya Zemlya archipelago, and the Barents Sea. (B) Difference between RSL and GMSL at Last Glacial Maximum (26 ka). (C) Timeseries of global mean sea level (GMSL, black) as well as relative sea level (RSL) at exemplary sites. Dashed green line indicates Last Glacial Maximum. (D) Difference between RSL and GMSL for exemplary sites. (E) Elevation of exemplary sites. Solid lines indicate elevation including GIA; dashed lines indicate elevation without GIA; the difference is highlighted in solid fill. Vertical dashes indicate times when each site is inundated in the GIA run but not the base run.

193 ing interglacials adds water to the ocean, which depresses the oceanic crust and elevates
 194 continental margins; ice sheet growth during glacials unloads oceans and causes conti-
 195 nental margin subsidence (Chappell, 1974). The hydro-isostatic effect is strongest in the
 196 Laptev, East Siberian, Chukchi Seas as well as on the Alaskan North Slope. During glacia-
 197 tions, water unloading leads to rebound of the oceans and subsidence of continents. Since
 198 the water masses rise with the rebounding ocean floor, sea level at the shelf break fol-
 199 lows the global mean while sea level at the modern coastline is higher than the global
 200 mean (Fig. 5C). This process is reversed during transgressions.

201 On average, the *GIA* run leads to higher sea level / lower elevations on the con-
 202 tinental shelf, which causes mean temperatures on the shelf to be warmer in the *GIA*
 203 run compared to the *base* run (Fig. 4B). This causes generally thinner subsea permafrost
 204 at the present in the *GIA* run compared to the *base* run (Fig. 2E). Inboard of the Lau-
 205 rentide and Eurasian peripheral bulges, the main *GIA* effect that influences permafrost
 206 is direct isostatic loading, which increases inundation (Fig. 5B). For example, along the
 207 western edge of Banks Island and in the Barents and Kara Seas, including *GIA* causes
 208 a thinning of present-day subsea permafrost that ranges from >200 m thinner on the deeper
 209 shelf to ~50 m thinner in the shallowest sediments (Fig. 2A). Beyond the peripheral bulge,
 210 hydro-isostasy causes cryotic sediment in areas of shallow bathymetry, such as the Laptev
 211 Sea, to thin by up to 50 m, while permafrost underlying deeper areas—e.g. distal parts
 212 of the East Siberian, Chukchi, and Beaufort Seas—thickens by up to 10 m.

213 In addition to this broad-stroke *GIA* signal, temperature and hence permafrost ext-
 214 tent is also dependent on the amount of time that the land is exposed. Land exposure
 215 time is a function of topography: *GIA* exposes shallow locations more frequently through-
 216 out glacial cycles, but deep locations only at the beginnings of glacial maxima (Fig. 5E).
 217 This leads to the more granular detail in the difference in permafrost thickness between
 218 the *GIA* run and the *base* run (Fig. 2E). In total, inclusion of *GIA* decreases the area
 219 of continental shelf underlain by subsea permafrost by 3×10^5 km² and the mean thick-
 220 ness of that permafrost by 11 m.

221 2.2 Future permafrost evolution

222 The future evolution of subsea permafrost depends on the amount of anthropogenic
 223 emissions in the next century. Under a low emissions scenario (SSP1-2.6), subsea per-
 224 mafrost as modeled in the *GIA* run will continue its historical rate of thinning to thin
 225 on average by ~30 m to a mean of ~211 m by 3000 CE. This thinning will be concen-
 226 trated in the central Laptev and Kara Seas due to the thicker present-day permafrost
 227 stocks in those areas. With low 21st century emissions, virtually no areas of seafloor presently
 228 underlain by permafrost will completely lose it in the next thousand years (Fig. 6). Un-
 229 der the high emissions scenario (SSP5-8.5), on the other hand, subsea permafrost will
 230 thin more than ~38 m everywhere by 2300 CE. This thinning will result in the disap-
 231 pearance of permafrost—with disappearance defined as permafrost thinning to <50 m—
 232 at the outer edge of the Russian arctic continental shelf and southern Alaska. By 3000
 233 CE, subsea permafrost will have thinned an average of ~153 m, a >60% loss relative to
 234 1850 CE, which will result in subsea permafrost disappearing from the Chukchi Sea, nearly
 235 all the Canadian arctic, much of the East Siberian Sea, and deep areas of the Laptev and
 236 Kara Seas.

237 There is strong correlation between the pre-industrial thickness of subsea permafrost
 238 and its time of disappearance (Fig. 7). Under low emissions, no permafrost thicker than
 239 100 m at 1850 CE thaws before 3000 CE. Under high emissions, all permafrost thinner
 240 than 100 m at 1850 CE, but none thicker than 200 m, disappears before 2300 CE. And
 241 by 3000 CE, under high emissions only permafrost more than 160 m thick at 1850 CE
 242 remains.

Figure 6. Modeled subsea permafrost loss percentage and thickness by 2300 and 3000 CE for low (SSP1-2.6) and high (SSP5-8.5) emissions scenarios.

Figure 7. Time when the permafrost at each location is thinner than 50 m for (A) *base* and (B) *GIA* run.

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2.2.1 *GIA effects on future subsea permafrost distribution*

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GIA affects future subsea permafrost in two ways: (1) 400,000 years of GIA influence leads to thinner present-day subsea permafrost in shallow-water regions (see Fig. 2), thereby reducing the thickness of the permafrost remaining and (2) GIA affects future sea-level change and causes local sea level to differ from the mean. The former is the significantly more important factor and has been described above. We will expand here on the latter.

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Future GIA acts to decrease RSL everywhere on the Arctic shelf, which has a small negative effect on the amount of future subsea permafrost. Less RSL rise decreases the area of newly flooded land, which leads to mean subsea permafrost thickness in the high emissions scenario thinning by ~ 3 m more by 3000 in the *GIA* run than in the *base* run. The GIA effect is modest relative to GMSL rise, however, which increases $8.6 \text{ m} \pm 4.6 \text{ m}$

255 by 3000 CE in the high emissions scenarios. During previous interglacials, rising sea level
256 temporarily increased mean subsea permafrost thickness by increasing the area of inun-
257 dation. However, when ocean bottom temperatures exceed 0 °C—projected to occur around
258 ~2100 CE with high future emissions (Wilkenskjeld et al., 2021)—any newly-flooded per-
259 mafrost will rapidly thaw from above as well as below. Beyond this ocean temperature
260 tipping point, future sea-level rise produces no gain in subsea permafrost.

261 The total effect of GIA causes earlier subsea permafrost disappearance. For instance,
262 all permafrost thinner than 100 m at 1850 disappears ~25 years faster in the *GIA* run
263 compared to the *base* run (2260 vs. 2290 CE, Fig. 7). And unlike in the *base* run, in the
264 *GIA* run no permafrost thicker than 200 m at 1850 CE disappears prior to 2400 CE (Fig.
265 7A).

266 3 Discussion

267 The large influence that different ice sheet histories have on our modeled present-
268 day subsea permafrost distributions highlights the role that late Quaternary ice sheets
269 play in permafrost formation. Ice sheets control permafrost directly beneath them be-
270 cause ice thickness and subglacial hydrology modulate sub-ice temperatures. It has also
271 long been known that terrestrial permafrost can influence ice sheet evolution (e.g. Lic-
272 ciardi et al., 1998; Clark et al., 1999; Tarasov & Peltier, 2007). We demonstrate that ice
273 sheets also influence subsea permafrost hundreds to thousands of kilometers distant due
274 to the gravitational and deformational effects of GIA. This finding supports a growing
275 body of evidence that climatic teleconnections have shaped permafrost evolution in the
276 20th century (e.g. Romanovsky et al., 2010) and the geologic past (e.g. Li et al., 2021),
277 and will likely continue to do so in the future (Ehlers et al., 2022).

278 Deep uncertainty, defined as uncertainty stemming from disagreement or ignorance
279 about the processes that drive a system, hampers precise projections of sea level over the
280 next century (Kopp et al., 2017, 2019). Projecting over the next millennium further ex-
281 pands the pool of uncertainty sources. Large uncertainties also surround ice sheet his-
282 tories for the past four glacial cycles.

283 While full quantification of these uncertainties is beyond the scope of this study,
284 first steps towards harnessing subsea permafrost as an ice sheet constraint are already
285 possible using our results. Using the ICE-6G ice history results in thinner permafrost
286 in the Eastern Laptev sea, a finding that better aligns with evidence from seismic sur-
287 veys suggesting that ice-bonded permafrost exists only in Eastern Laptev sediments in-
288 board of the 60 m isobath (Bogoyavlensky et al., 2023). Use of the ICE-6G ice history
289 also increases the modeled thickness and lower boundary of present-day ice-saturated
290 subsea permafrost on the Beaufort shelf (Fig. 2D). This finding better aligns with seis-
291 mic and borehole data that find the lowermost ice-saturated permafrost in the Beaufort
292 Sea at an average depth of 500 m (Canadian) and 460 m (Alaskan), and mean thickness
293 of Alaskan Beaufort Sea ice-saturated sediments of 200 m (Fig. 8, Ruppel & Kessler,
294 2017; Hu et al., 2013). Improved data-model fit indicates that the combination of ICE6G
295 and the Waelbroeck et al. (2002) GMSL curve may represent the Beaufort Sea’s history
296 of ice cover, inundation, and subaerial exposure better than CLIMBER2 and the GMSL
297 curve from Grant et al. (2014) do.

298 However, modeled Beaufort Sea permafrost in the *GIA* run is still significantly thin-
299 ner and shallower than observations, suggesting that subsea permafrost in this region
300 may be influenced by processes not accounted for in our model. These processes include
301 permafrost formation beneath shallow ice sheet margins, spatial variations in benthic tem-
302 peratures driven by inflow of warm Atlantic water into the Arctic, changes in river and
303 drainage basins, and spatiotemporally discrete sedimentation and erosion events such
304 as glaciogenic debris flows, the transgression of which would produce additional syngenetic

Figure 8. Comparison of borehole observations to modeled values for the depth of the low-est ice saturated cell (A, C) and the length of the depth interval of ice-saturated sediment (B, D). Borehole data from the Canadian (A, B Hu et al., 2013) and Alaskan (C, D ?, ?) Beaufort shelf regions are compared to modeled values from the three runs (*legacy*, *base* and *GIA*) for all modeled locations bounded by the borehole coordinates. Note that the depth interval of ice-saturated sediment is not calculable from Hu et al. (2013)

305 subsea permafrost. Though inclusion of these factors exceeds this study’s scope, they likely
 306 have significant impacts on subsea permafrost formation and should be included in fu-
 307 ture pan-Arctic permafrost models.

308 Beyond the Beaufort and Eastern Laptev Seas, the lack of observational constraints
 309 leaves the updates in subsea permafrost distribution made here open to future observa-
 310 tional ground-truthing. Such is the case off the west coast of Banks Island, Canada, where
 311 our *GIA* run predicts no subsea permafrost but P. P. Overduin et al. (2019) map sub-
 312 sea permafrost that in places exceeds 200 m. Should future observational campaigns tar-
 313 get regions such as Banks Island or the eastern Kara Sea, they will have the added ben-
 314 efit of constraining not only subsea permafrost itself but also the local glaciation histo-
 315 ries of the Eurasian and Laurentide ice sheets.

316 Future work should focus investigation of the sensitivity of present-day permafrost
 317 to ice sheet variations during times when ice histories are especially uncertain. Those
 318 times include the LGM, where ice sheet modeling continues to disagree with sea level
 319 estimates of global ice volume (Simms et al., 2019); MIS-3 (57 kyr to 34 kyr BP, Rails-
 320 back et al., 2015)), when recent evidence suggests GMSL may have been more than 20 m
 321 higher than modeled here (Waelbroeck et al., 2002; Pico et al., 2018; Dalton et al., 2022;
 322 Farmer et al., 2023); and the penultimate deglaciation, when the size of the EIS and its
 323 collapse history remain largely uncertain (Dendy et al., 2017). Future work could also

324 test subsea permafrost’s sensitivity to the history of the Siberian ice sheet, which dur-
325 ing the penultimate and earlier glacial cycles may have held significant mass (? , ?). Dif-
326 ferences in ice sheet loading during these intervals, and the accompanying sea-level vari-
327 ations, would produce characteristic spatial signatures in present-day permafrost. This
328 line of inquiry points to subsea permafrost as an as-yet-untapped constraint on past ice
329 sheet histories.

330 The analysis of subsea permafrost presented here has implications for the amount
331 of organic carbon that subsea permafrost presently holds and therefore its potential as
332 a future emitter of greenhouse gases. Recent structured expert assessment of subsea per-
333 mafrost places present-day stocks of organic carbon and methane, respectively, at ~ 560
334 (170–740, 90 % confidence interval) and 45 (10–110) gigatons of carbon, and projects that
335 subsea permafrost could emit 190 (45–590) Gt CO₂-equivalent (Sayedi et al., 2020). Our
336 work suggests that present-day subsea permafrost is thinner than previously thought in
337 shallow regions and in the western Russian arctic, in some areas by several hundred met-
338 ters. We also find that the area of seafloor presently underlain by subsea permafrost is
339 $>25\%$ smaller than previously estimated. These findings reduce both the amount of or-
340 ganic carbon that subsea permafrost may hold and the amount of greenhouse gases that
341 it may, through future thaw, release, though lack of consensus remains about what pro-
342 portion of the CO₂ and methane released by subsea permafrost reaches the atmosphere
343 (Mestdagh et al., 2017; Portnov et al., 2014). Projecting into the future, our results con-
344 strain the spatial distribution of future permafrost loss as well as the pace of its thaw.
345 These findings can inform present planning for future community-based and industrial
346 undertakings on the Arctic continental shelf, as such activities rely on accurate assess-
347 ment of subsurface sediment characteristics.

348 Comparison of future climate projections with paleoclimatic analogues can give per-
349 spective on the effect that human activity has had on the climate system. We provide
350 this context by comparing our projected rates of future subsea permafrost thinning to
351 thinning rates over the past four glacial cycles (Fig. 9). Mean rates of past subsea per-
352 mafrost thinning during interstadials have ranged from 5 m/kyr during MIS-9c to 31.2 m/kyr
353 during MIS-7e (Fig. 9). In previous interglacial periods during which average subsea per-
354 mafrost thickness exceeded 200 m, e.g. MIS 9e, 9a, 7e, 5e, 1, subsea permafrost thinned
355 at an average rate of ~ 27 m/kyr. We project that subsea permafrost will thaw at a rate
356 similar to 1850 speeds until 2050 (29 m/kyr) regardless of emissions scenario. After 2050,
357 human activity in the 21st century will have a significant effect on subsea permafrost thin-
358 ning rates. Under low emissions scenarios, the present rate of thinning continues to 3000
359 CE. High 21st century emissions, however, will accelerate thinning between 2050 and 2350
360 CE to > 8 times faster than the fastest thinning rate since MIS-9. Between 2350 and
361 3000 CE, thinning rates remain at 110 m/kyr, which is roughly four times faster than
362 pre-industrial values.

363 Subsea permafrost thaw accelerates under the high emissions scenarios because the
364 Arctic passes a climate tipping point. Loss of Arctic sea ice, included in our model via
365 the modeled bottom water temperatures from Wilkenskjeld et al. (2021), spurs the Arc-
366 tic to warm at a rate faster than the global mean (Dai et al., 2019). The positive feed-
367 back loop inherent in Arctic amplification – wherein lost sea ice lowers Arctic albedo,
368 which hastens sea ice loss – leads to cascading effects on the Arctic climate system. These
369 effects include the warming of Arctic shelf waters above zero degrees (Wilkenskjeld et
370 al., 2021), a tipping point past which subsea permafrost thaw accelerates as it melts from
371 both above and below. Though this acceleration is avoided under the low emissions sce-
372 nario, under the high emissions scenario the tipping point occurs at ~ 2050 CE.

Figure 9. Mean thickness change rates between 400 kyr BP and 3000 CE. Horizontal lines denote mean rates of subsea permafrost thinning for each Marine Isotope Stage (MIS) during which subsea permafrost existed and for future predictions.

373 4 Conclusion

374 Our new pan-Arctic simulation of subsea permafrost from 400 kyr BP to 3000 CE
 375 enables an updated assessment of the history, present-day characteristics, and future evo-
 376 lution of subsea permafrost that accounts for the effects of GIA. We find that GIA in-
 377 fluences subsea permafrost evolution everywhere on the continental shelf, with the de-
 378 formational effects of ice sheet loading dominant in the Barents, Kara, and Beaufort Seas,
 379 and hydro-isostasy dominant in the Laptev, East Siberian, and Chukchi Seas. Our new
 380 subsea permafrost map based on the *GIA* run has 14 % less seafloor area underlain by
 381 permafrost and is 4.2 % thinner than the same run without GIA. Both runs update the
 382 ice cover and sea level forcing of the legacy run (cf. P. P. Overduin et al., 2019) result-
 383 ing in even less permafrost (by 14 % area and 8 % thickness). The recent IPCC-AR6 re-
 384 port suggests that future permafrost thaw would be insufficient to trigger self-reinforcing
 385 acceleration in climate warming (Chen et al., 2021). The same is not true of the future
 386 effects of climate warming on subsea permafrost. Under a high emissions scenario that
 387 includes the loss of year-round Arctic sea ice, which is included in our modeling, self-reinforcing
 388 feedbacks in the climate system trigger rapid, irreversible acceleration of subsea permafrost
 389 thaw that begins in the next 30 years and persists so long as ocean bottom temperatures
 390 exceed 0 °C. This possible future adds yet more urgency to efforts to slow human emis-
 391 sion of greenhouse gases in the next quarter century.

392 5 Methods

393 5.1 Permafrost model

394 Permafrost extent and composition were calculated from the output of a 1-D heat
 395 transfer model. We used CryoGrid 2, a 1-D heat diffusion model introduced by Westermann
 396 et al. (2013), which is a model that continues to develop. The current version is described
 397 in a release paper (Westermann et al., 2022) and the code is available at

398 https://github.com/CryoGrid/CryoGridCommunity_source/releases/tag/GMD

399 (accessed 20.05.2022). The model was implemented similarly to the implementa-
 400 tion in P. P. Overduin et al. (2019), save that we changed the synthesized forcing tem-
 401 perature by using different sources for sea level, ice sheet histories, and began the model
 402 at 400 ka rather than 450 ka. We performed calculations at grid cell centers of the 12.5 km

EASE Grid 2.0 (Brodzik et al., 2012) and included any locations with modern elevations between 187 m below and 18 m above sea level (bsl, asl, Jakobsson et al., 2020).

Boundary conditions

The lower boundary condition for permafrost was temporally invariant heat flux drawn from the globally distributed data of Davies (2013). The upper boundary condition was temperature, either land surface, seabed or subglacial, as described in the following.

Historical land surface temperature was forced with air temperature from the CLIMBER2 intermediate complexity Earth System Model (Ganopolski et al., 2010). Under conditions of future sea-level change, some modeled locations may submerge or emerge, and thus require forcing with future land surface temperatures until submergence or following emergence. This applied to only a few locations in our modelling domain, usually next to the coast. In these few cases, constant temperatures equivalent to those during pre-industrial time (1850 CE) were applied. Though permafrost was removed from present-day locations where warm bottom water in deltaic and estuarine settings likely precludes permafrost formation, no assumptions were made about the locations of paleo rivers and estuaries. This likely results in a minor overestimation of subsea permafrost in those regions.

Historical seabed temperatures were forced as a function of water depth, based on observational data from the Siberian shelf area (Dmitrenko et al., 2011). Reductions in ice cover extent and duration are expected to warm the seabed since brine produced by freezing sea ice cools the seabed. Wilkenskjeld et al. (2021) shows warming of the seabed by up to 10 °C under more severe climate change scenarios such as Shared Socioeconomic Pathway 8.5 (SSP5-8.5) (Supplemental Fig. S2). The increase in seabed temperatures is strongly related to disappearance of sea ice. Our future seabed temperature forcing was adjusted by the spatial-mean anomaly of projected decadal mean seabed temperatures for either a low (SSP1-2.6) or high (SSP5-8.5) emissions scenario (Wilkenskjeld et al., 2021) from 1850 to 2950 CE, consistent for each run with the corresponding ice sheet model forcing (Tab. S1). Temperatures from 2950 to 3000 CE were held constant at 2950 CE level. Subglacial temperatures were treated as warm-based for ice masses exceeding 100 m in thickness and set to 0 °C, as in P. P. Overduin et al. (2019).

5.2 Glacial Isostatic Adjustment model

GIA was calculated following the algorithm of Kendall et al. (2005), which computes gravitationally self-consistent sea-level variations that are caused by ice and liquid water loading on a viscoelastic earth. Calculations include the effects of shoreline migration and the impact of load-induced Earth rotation changes on sea level (Mitrovica et al., 2005; Milne & Mitrovica, 1998). We assume a radially symmetric viscoelastic Earth structure with a viscosity following the VM5 profile (Peltier et al., 2015) and the elastic structure and density from the PREM seismic model (Dziewonski & Anderson, 1981).

Ice history 400 ka to 2015 CE

Our ice history from the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM) to 1950 CE follows ICE-6G (Peltier et al., 2015). The ICE-6G history was then extended back over four glacial cycles following the GMSL curve from Waelbroeck et al. (2002), which is based on RSL observations and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ records from benthic foraminifera (Fig. 3). Ice sheet geometries prior to the LGM were chosen by finding the post-LGM ICE-6G geometry that best matches each pre-LGM GMSL value. For GMSL values prior to LGM that fall outside of the range of LGM to present values, we assume the closest available GMSL value. This assumption resulted in a present-day GMSL during MIS-9e and 5e since no template of ice col-

lapse is available in the ICE-6G deglacial history. Though these times have higher than modern GMSL (e.g. de Gelder et al., 2022), this approximation is expected to have a negligible effect on the results presented here. There is evidence that the ice sheet configuration during the penultimate glacial maximum differed significantly from that during the last glacial maximum (Batchelor et al., 2019). We therefore followed the approach of Dendy et al. (2017) replacing the EIS geometries between 200 and 130 ka with reconstructions from (Lambeck, 1995; Lambeck et al., 2006) and pairing them with Laurentide ice sheet geometries chosen from the post-LGM ICE-6G history in order to maintain the GMSL curve of (Waelbroeck et al., 2002).

For the ice geometry between 1950 and 2015, we used the ice thickness from the Ice Sheet Model Intercomparison Project (ISMIP6, S. M. J. Nowicki et al., 2016; S. Nowicki et al., 2020). ICE-6G's 1950 CE ice extent is not in full agreement with the 1950 CE ice thicknesses from the Ice Sheet Model Intercomparison Project (ISMIP6, S. M. J. Nowicki et al., 2016; S. Nowicki et al., 2020). We therefore constructed a smooth transition from ICE6G to ISMIP6 ice extents by tapering the difference between the two models from 0% to 100% between 0 CE and 1950 CE, then added it to ICE6G. The GIA simulation was run from 400 kyr BP to 1950 CE with time steps of 100 yr, which were interpolated using nearest neighbour interpolation to the 100 yr timesteps of the permafrost simulation.

Ice history 2015 to 3000 CE

Between 2015 and 3000 we used an ensemble of 17 Antarctic and 14 Greenland ice models from the SICOPOLIS polythermal ice-sheet model (Greve, Calov, et al., 2020; Greve, Chambers, & Calov, 2020), which, following the ISMIP6 protocol, were produced with dynamic oceanic and atmospheric forcing between 2015 and the end of 2100 and constant forcing through 3000. See Chambers et al. (2021) and Greve and Chambers (2021) for full details on Antarctic and Greenland, respectively. AIS and GIS ensemble members with identical Generalized Circulation Model (GCM) forcing, ocean forcing, and emissions scenario (SSP/RCP) were paired. AIS members with no identical GIS analogues were paired with a GIS member produced by the same emissions scenario. See Table S1 for details the list of GIS/AIS pairings. The GIA simulation was run with time steps between 10 yr and 100 yr, which were interpolated using nearest neighbour interpolation to the 10 yr timesteps of the permafrost simulation.

5.3 Permafrost Model Output and Data Analysis

Model output included sediment temperature and composition at 2 m spacing over depth to 2 km below the land surface or seabed, at the modeled EASE Grid 2.0 locations. The temporal resolution of the output is 100 yr for the historic period until 1850 CE and 10 yr for the future projections.

The model was run over all possible permafrost locations, i.e. all locations on the EASE Grid 2.0 with current elevation between -187 and 18 masl as this encompasses the maximum range of RSL change in the forcing data. We also applied a filter to rule out locations in big river deltas and estuaries, including grid cells near the Ob and Lena rivers, St. Petersburg Gulf, the Baltic Sea, near Iceland, south of Kamchatka, and in the Bering Strait. Results were then further filtered, to include only locations that a) have been subaerial for at least 100 yr during the model period, b) are currently submerged and c) have modern permafrost deeper than what a theoretical modern steady state solution yields (cf. P. P. Overduin et al., 2019).

To evaluate possible future thinning rates of subsea permafrost, we calculated the mean projected thinning rates within the low (SPP1-2.6) and high (SSP5-8.5) emissions scenarios for the historic period (1850 - 2020 CE), the near future (2020 - 2300 CE) and

500 the distant future (2300 - 3000 CE). For comparison, we calculated the mean thinning
501 rate between minimum and maximum mean permafrost thickness for each MIS.

502 We compare our modeled lower permafrost bound to observations determined using
503 a combination of well-log and temperature records from the Beaufort shelf (Canadian:
504 Hu et al. (2013); Alaskan: Ruppel and Kessler (2017)). Most well-log records vary
505 as a function of ice saturation of the sediment pore space (e.g. bulk sediment propagation
506 velocity or electrical resistivity), whereas our modeled values reflect the depth of the
507 0°C isotherm. Values from Ruppel and Kessler (2017) are based on their assessment of
508 intermediate ice saturation; only permafrost lower limit observations with a data quality
509 of a or b were included from Hu et al. (2013). All modeled grid cells within the longitudinal
510 range covered by the industry wells, are included, i.e. from the coastline out to
511 the outer edge of permafrost occurrence. The proximity of the industry wells to the shoreline
512 skews to thicker permafrost.

513 Observed lower bounds of permafrost are deeper than our models produce, and differences
514 between the model runs are smaller (<55 m) than between mean modeled and
515 mean observed (298 m, Ruppel and 274 m, Hu).

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